

INFLUENCE OF NON-ELECTROLYTES ON THE DECOMPOSITION POTENTIAL OF AQUEOUS SILVER NITRATE

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Decomposition potential of aqueous silver nitrate ($N/10$) has been measured at 30° , in presence of the non-electrolytes: ethyl alcohol, glycerine, acetone and pyridine, whose concentrations have been varied within wide limits. Results show that the above quantity for silver nitrate practically remains unaltered despite the presence of large proportions of the non-electrolytes (except acetone) in the system. These together with the results with acetone are discussed. The data are also given for the conductivities of the corresponding solutions.

Le Blanc (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1891, 8, 299; 1893, 12, 333; 'A Text Book of Electrochemistry' MacMillan Co., London, 1920, Chap. VIII, p. 289) was the first to measure the decomposition voltages of acids, bases and salts in aqueous solutions. The work was further extended by subsequent investigators to a large number of salts, both in aqueous* and non-aqueous† solutions. The limitations of the graphical method have been pointed out by many workers**. The influence of the electrode material on the decomposition potential was studied by Coehn and Dannenberg (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1901, 38, 609) and Caspari (*ibid.*, 1899, 30, 86), and of irradiation of the electrodes by Leighton (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1913, 17, 695).

The experiments were carried out with a view to examining the influence of medium on the decomposition potential of silver nitrate in presence of some non-electrolytes.

EXPERIMENTAL

The chemicals employed were Merck's reagents. Ethyl alcohol, acetone and pyridine were freshly distilled before use. Pure glycerol was used. A stock solution of $N/5$ - AgNO_3 was prepared. In all the following experiments 50 c.c. of the stock solution diluted to 100 c.c. with the requisite amount of nonelectrolyte and water, were used for electrolysis. The electrolysis was carried out in a conductivity cell between two bright platinum electrodes, each of 1 sq. cm. area, fixed vertically, the inter-electrode distance being 1.2 cm. The cell was kept immersed in a water thermostat maintained at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The platinum electrodes before use were properly cleaned; they were placed in $N/10$ - AgNO_3 solution and short-circuited for several hours (*cf.* Findlay, "Practical Physical Chemistry", Longmans, Green & Co., London, 1933, p. 205) until they no longer gave any detectable κ -m.f. when placed in the same solution. A storage battery (6 volts) was closed through a suitable resistance furnished with a sliding contact. A gradually increasing potential was applied to the poles of the cell containing the solution under investigation and the current passing was read on a precision milliammeter. The potential applied was measured by the potentiometer, supplied by the Cambridge Instrument Co., Ltd. It was worked on a steady

* *cf.* Smale, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1894, 14, 577; Glaser, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1898, 8, 373, 424; Kudra, *Mem. Inst. Chem. Ukrain Acad. Sci.*, 1938, 8, 127, 177; *cf.* also Heyrovsky and co-workers, *Die Polarographische Methode in Bottger, "Physikalische Methoden der Chemischen Analyse," Leipzig.*

† *cf.* Muller and Duschek, *Monatsh*, 1922, 48, 75; Mason and Mathews, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 1379; Finkelstein, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1925, 118, 303; Biswas and Bose, *ibid.*, 1927, 128, 442; Evans, Lee and Lee, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 489.

** *cf.* Rmil Bose, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1898, 8, 153; Westhaver, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1905, 81, 65; Bennetitz, *ibid.*, 1920, 72, 202; *cf.* also Ferguson and van Zyl, *Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1924, 68, 337.

2 volt battery and was adjusted before use by using Weston's standard cadmium cell and was checked after the completion of an experiment. Each experiment was repeated at least twice using fresh solution and cleaned electrodes. The current-voltage values are shown in Table I and also graphically in Fig. 1.

TABLE I*

Current-voltage values for
 $N/10$ - $AgNO_3$.
Temp. = 30° .

Applied potential in volts.	Current in milliamps.	Applied potential in volts.	Current in milliamps.	Vol. of KOH in 100 c.c. soln.
0.613	0	0.931	1.0	0 c.c.
0.649	0	0.992	2.0	5
0.720	0	1.034	3.1	10
0.738	0	1.099	4.5	25
0.783	0.08	1.137	5.6	50
0.828	0.15	1.208	7.5	
0.845	0.22	1.250	8.7	
0.869	0.37	1.307	10.4	
0.888	0.50	1.428	13.7	

TABLE II

Influence of ethyl alcohol.
Conc. of $AgNO_3 = N/10$
Temp. = 30° .

Decomposition voltage	Resistance (ohms.)	Sp. condy. (mhos.)
0.75	33.5	0.01127
0.75	35	0.01079
0.75	37	0.01021
0.75	52	0.00726
0.75	77.5	0.00487

TABLE III

Influence of glycerol.
Conc. of $AgNO_3 = N/10$.
Temp. = 30° .

Vol. of glycerol in 200 c.c. soln.	Decomposition voltage (graphical).	Resistance (ohm.)	Sp. condy. (mhos.)
0 c.c.	0.75	33.5	0.01127
5	0.75	35	0.01079
10	0.75	40	0.00944
25	0.75	55	0.00687
50	0.75	121	0.00312

* Table I serves as a specimen table, where the current-voltage values are given. In Tables II-V only the final results obtained from graphs (cf. curves 2-5 in Fig. 1) are shown.

TABLE IV

Influence of acetone.

Other conditions same as in Table III.

Vol. of acetone in 100 c.c. soln.	Decomposition voltage (graphical).	Resistance.	Sp. condy.
0 c.c.	0.75	33.5 ohm.	0.01127 mho.
5	0.85	34	0.01111
10	0.85	36	0.01049
50	0.85	56	0.00674

TABLE V

Influence of pyridine.

Other conditions same as in Table III.

Vol. of pyridine in 100 c.c. soln.	Decomposition voltage (graphical).	Resistance.	Sp. condy.
0 c.c.	0.75	33.5 ohm.	0.01127 mho.
5	0.75	51	0.00740
10	0.75	55	0.00687
25	0.75	67	0.00564

The electrolytic resistances of the solutions used in this work were determined on a Post Office box with the usual precautions. These values are shown in Tables II-V.

DISCUSSION

The foregoing results in Table I indicate the variation of the current as shown by the milliammeter when a gradually increasing potential is applied to the electrodes. At first, an almost zero

or very small current, the residual current, is obtained, but after the applied E.M.F. reaches a certain value, the current begins to increase rapidly with increase in the applied E.M.F. The point, where this rapid increase in the electrolysing current commences, is the *decomposition potential* of the solution under consideration. A sudden and marked change in the direction of the curve obtained by plotting the applied E.M.F. against the current strength (*cf.* Fig. 1) indicates the decomposition point. This is in agreement with the general findings of the earlier workers, Le Blanc (*loc. cit.*), Glaser (*loc. cit.*), Emil Bose (*loc. cit.*), Bennowitz (*loc. cit.*) and others. When a dilute solution of silver nitrate is electrolysed between platinum electrodes, silver is deposited on the cathode and oxygen is liberated at the anode. A cell of the type, Ag | solution | O₂, is set up, which exhibits a certain E.M.F. due to the tendency of the silver and oxygen to pass back into the ionic state. The E.M.F. of the cell acts in a direction opposite to that of the electrolysing current. In order, therefore, that continuous electrolysis may take place, an E.M.F. must be applied to the electrodes sufficient to overcome the back E.M.F. of the products of electrolysis. This explains why a certain minimum potential is necessary to induce continuous decomposition in an electrolyte (*cf.* also Le Blanc, *loc. cit.*).

The value recorded in the present paper for the decomposition potential, obtained by the graphical method is 0.75 volt for $N/10$ -AgNO₃ at 30°; Le Blanc (*loc. cit.*) gives 0.70 volt for N -AgNO₃, presumably at 20°. The observed increase from 0.7 to 0.75 volt might be mainly due to a decrease in concentration of AgNO₃ solution from N to $N/10$, since temperature coefficient of the decomposition potential is negligibly low, 0.0008 volt per degree (*cf.* Wilkinson and Gillet, *loc. cit.*). It is well known that a smaller E.M.F. is required to separate an ion from a concentrated solution than from a dilute one (*cf.* Le Blanc, *loc. cit.*, Bose, *loc. cit.* and Wilkinson and Gillet, *loc. cit.*).

Results with ethyl alcohol (Table II) and glycerine (Table III) show that the decomposition potential of $N/10$ -AgNO₃ remains almost unaltered, despite the addition of varying amounts (5 to 50%) of the nonelectrolyte (curves 2, 3 in Fig. 1). It is interesting to note that the changes (though of a considerable magnitude in some cases) in physical properties of the medium such as the viscosity, density, conductivity, and dielectric constant, seem to have no effect on the decomposition potential of AgNO₃. This might probably be attributed to the absence of interaction between the ions of the solute and the medium. Similar were the conclusions of Biswas and Bose (*loc. cit.*), who observed that the presence of water in methyl alcohol solutions of KI and KBr had very little influence on the corresponding current-voltage curves. But the presence of water in methyl alcohol solutions of HCl and LiCl had a marked influence on the decomposition potentials; this was attributed by the authors to the combination of the solute with the solvent. Contrary views are held regarding the influence of the medium on the transport number of the silver ion in silver nitrate. Carrara (*Gazzetta*, 1903, 33, 241) assumed that no complex ion was found in the medium, while others notably Krumreich (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1916, 22, 446) found it necessary to assume the formation of an alcohol-water complex (and not the solute-solvent complex) to account for the maximum in the transport number curve. Carrara's conclusions were further criticised by Lapworth and Partington (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 98, 1417). Jones and Basset (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1904, 32, 409) and Jones and Rouiller (*ibid.*, 1906, 38, 427) determined the relative migration velocities of the ions of silver nitrate in water, methyl and ethyl alcohol, acetone and in binary mixtures of these solvents together with the conductivity of such solutions. The relative migration velocities are influenced largely by the nature of the solvent and in mixed solvents are found to vary both

with temperature and composition of the mixture probably due to the varying degrees of combination of the solvent with one of these ions.

The results in Tables II and III have already been explained on the assumption that the ions of the solute, *viz.*, AgNO_3 , form no complex with the medium. It is, however, very likely that the added non-electrolyte (ethyl alcohol, glycerol) might form complexes with water, the exact composition of the complex depending upon the nature of the non-electrolyte and the relative proportions of the two. Sufficient evidence is available in the literature to show this possibility. Krumreich (*loc. cit.*) from transport number measurements of AgNO_3 in ethyl alcohol-water mixtures brought out evidence for the existence of alcohol-water complex. Complex of the type, $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH} \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, corresponding to 50% alcohol, has been shown to exist beyond doubt by Dorochevski and Roshestwenski (*J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 40, 860) from conductivity measurements and by Hess (*Ann. Physik*, 1908, 27, 609) from volume contraction measurements. This is also in agreement with the views of Getman, Dunstan and Traube ("Viscosity," Monogram on Inorganic and Physical Chemistry Series, 1914). Glycerine is also known to form complexes with water. It should, however, be stressed at this stage that the existence of such water-alcohol or water-glycerine complexes in the medium may not, it is to be anticipated, alter the decomposition potential of a dissolved solute (AgNO_3), provided the solute itself takes no part in complex formation with the medium, or its heat of solution is not affected appreciably. This follows from the fact that the decomposition potential of a solute is a thermodynamical quantity and should, therefore, correspond to the energy equal to the heat of formation of the solute from its ions.

Results with increasing proportion of pyridine (up to 25%) also indicate that the decomposition potential of silver nitrate remains unaltered, *i.e.*, 0.75 volt (Table V and Fig. 1). The above explanation might suitably account for the observed results provided AgNO_3 forms no complex with pyridine. Schlundt (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1902, 6, 159) from transport number measurements of Ag^+ -ion from AgNO_3 in anhydrous pyridine, observed that AgNO_3 forms a complex with pyridine (*cf.* also Neustadt and Abegg, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1909, 69, 486). Furthermore, Muller and Duschek (*loc. cit.*) determined the decomposition potentials of AgNO_3 in anhydrous pyridine. The values reported are 2.15 and 2.05 volts for $N/10$ - AgNO_3 and N - AgNO_3 respectively. The abnormally high value 2.15 volts for $N/10$ - AgNO_3 in pyridine obtained by Muller and Duschek (*loc. cit.*) as compared with the present value 0.75 volt in water (Table I) and in various mixtures

Fig. 1

of water and pyridine (Table V) might possibly be ascribed to the existence of silver nitrate-pyridine complexes in the former. Since the decomposition potential is not altered (*cf.* Fig. 1) though the proportion of pyridine in water-pyridine mixtures is varied up to 25%, it appears that silver nitrate-pyridine complex may not exist under the stated conditions, probably due to the decomposing action of water which is in a relatively larger proportion (*cf.* Henderson, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1907, 59, 118; 1908, 63, 325).

From the data returned in Table IV (curve 4 in Fig. 1) it is seen that the presence of acetone, (5%) raises the decomposition potential from 0.75 to 0.85 volt. Its increased concentration (up to 50%), however, produces no further change in the above quantity. This might probably be due to the formation of a stable complex of silver nitrate with acetone present in the various acetone-water mixtures used. It is also probable that the heat of the solution of silver nitrate might be affected considerably by acetone present in the system; this, however, might not happen in the case of ethyl alcohol, glycerol and pyridine.

It became necessary for the interpretation of the results obtained to determine the conductivities of the solutions used in this work. These data are shown in Tables II-V. Schall (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1894, 14, 701) found that the conductivity is usually decreased when water is replaced in part by alcohol in solution, which is in agreement with the foregoing results. Hantzsch (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1900, 25, 332) studied the influence of non-electrolyte on the conductivity of electrolytes. The addition of methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol and acetone to aqueous solutions of the alkali and alkaline-earth metals diminished the conductivity slightly and approximately to the same extent.

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